

Kinetics of Aquation of Bromopentamminecobalt(III) Perchlorate in Mixed Aqueous Solvents

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The aquation kinetics of bromopentamminecobalt(III) ion have been investigated in glycerol-water and n-propanol-water mixtures at 35-60°. The variation of the thermodynamic parameters ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger with the mole fraction of the organic solvent is discussed. Moreover, the linear isokinetic plots reveal the existence of a compensation effect due to a strong solute-solvent interaction. Finally the rate coefficients are correlated with both the dielectric constant of the medium and the water concentration according to recently proposed equations.

In studying the reaction kinetics of coordination compounds in solution, an increasing attention has been paid to the influence of solvent. Many useful information have been obtained mainly by studying rates for the spontaneous aquation of some halogenopentamminechromium(III) and -cobalt(III) ions, in a range of binary mixed solvents¹. In determining the mechanism, correlations of the rate constant with the dielectric constant of the solvent or with functions derived by linear free energy relations² are studied. The values of the rate constants and the thermodynamic activation parameters can be related with quantities characterising the structure of the mixed solvent³.

The aim of the present work is devoted to the aquation of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ in a wide concentration range of glycerol-water and n-propanol-water mixtures. These solvent media provide a useful range of dielectric constant and medium effects.

Results and Discussion

The rates of aquation have been measured in n-propanol-water and glycerol-water media of different compositions (10-70%, w/w) in the temperature range 30-60°. The reaction mixtures were slightly acidified with perchloric acid (0.033 M) in order to suppress the formation of the corresponding hydroxo complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$. The observed first order rate constants (k) for different temperatures and compositions were computed from the slopes of linear least-squares first order plots. The data are collected in Table 1. The isocomposition activation energy (E_c) and $\log(A)$ were computed from the best fitted Arrhenius plots. The observed first order rate constant at different temperatures decreased upon increasing the mole fraction of the co-solvent. One explanation of this result is that a water molecule, bound by hydrogen bond to a solvent molecule, is less nucleophilic than a water molecule hydrogen-bonded to another water molecule. Also, the addition of an organic co-solvent appeared to stabilise the

complex ion (initial state) and this contributes to an increase in ΔG^\ddagger and thus a decrease in the rate constant. As a result, rates of S_N1 solvolysis of organic halides⁴ and of aquation of cobalt(III)amine or amine halide complexes⁵ always decrease as the proportion of the non-aqueous component increases, and it can be ascribed to the smaller dielectric constant which usually discourages halide ion dissociation.

The thermodynamic activation parameters ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are listed in Table 2. Fig. 1 represents the variations of these parameters with the mole fraction of the studied solvents. It is clear from the figure that ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger curves, in both the solvents, exhibit one maximum. These maxima are at the mole fractions 0.189 and 0.176 in case of n-propanol-water and glycerol-water mixtures, respectively. This behaviour can be visualised in the light of change of water structure^{6,7} in the presence of aliphatic alcohol. It is known that the exact nature of liquid water is not well understood⁸. Many of its properties suggest that it is a mixture of fluctuating regions of three-dimensional hydrogen-bonded polymers in equilibrium with randomly arranged water monomer molecules⁹. Pure aliphatic alcohols also have a considerable fraction of their molecules joined in rings and chains, but they do not seem to participate in the formation of the three-dimensional clusters characteristic of water⁷. It was supposed that when an alcohol is added to pure water, the structure of the latter would be destroyed progressively as the alcohol content increases. However, the plots of activation enthalpy and entropy against the mole fraction exhibit maxima and minima. This type of variation associated with the solvent-shell reorganisation of the complex ions both in the initial and in the transition states contributes appreciably to the overall activation enthalpy and entropy of the aquation reaction¹⁰. It was supposed that when an alcohol is added to pure water the structure of the latter would be destroyed progressively as the alcohol content increases.

The addition of an alcohol to water causes at first an in-

TABLE 1—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (k , s^{-1}), $E_b/\log(c/D)$ and $\log(A/k)$

Wt. %	Glycerol				n-Propanol			
	$10^5 k$	D	$\frac{E_b}{\log(c/D)}$	$\log(A/k)$	$10^5 k$	D	$\frac{E_b}{\log(c/D)}$	$\log(A/k)$
	Temp. = 303.15 K				Temp. = 308.15 K			
10	1.053	73.94	305.4	15.95	1.444	68.38	298.5	15.59
20	0.969	71.20	307.9	16.08	1.306	61.76	287.5	15.09
30	0.946	68.36	303.8	15.86	1.293	54.78	277.5	14.55
40	0.846	65.45	296.1	15.47	1.271	47.67	299.9	15.68
50	0.798	62.43	296.7	15.49	1.244	40.65	295.5	15.42
60	0.733	58.48	299.2	15.63	1.096	34.37	286.9	15.02
70	0.426	54.24	322.0	16.85	0.972	28.90	279.6	14.60
	Temp. = 313.15 K				Temp. = 318.15 K			
10	3.198	70.41	295.4	15.47	4.756	65.15	289.1	15.07
20	3.028	67.70	297.6	15.59	4.568	58.76	278.5	14.54
30	2.727	64.87	293.3	15.40	4.389	52.02	268.8	14.02
40	2.686	62.03	285.8	14.97	4.219	45.17	290.5	15.16
50	2.341	59.55	287.7	15.02	3.717	38.44	286.2	14.94
60	2.347	55.48	289.3	15.13	3.714	32.43	277.9	14.49
70	1.739	51.41	311.1	16.24	2.969	27.21	271.1	14.12
	Temp. = 323.15 K				Temp. = 323.15 K			
10	9.930	67.22	286.5	14.98	7.767	63.59	284.6	14.86
20	9.079	64.67	288.8	15.11	7.479	57.32	274.2	14.33
30	8.729	62.04	284.9	14.89	7.222	50.69	264.6	13.80
40	7.639	59.31	277.8	14.52	7.143	43.96	286.0	14.93
50	6.674	56.49	278.3	14.56	6.436	37.38	281.8	14.71
60	6.105	52.84	280.7	14.71	6.049	31.51	273.6	14.28
70	4.818	49.01	302.0	15.80	4.834	26.41	267.0	13.91
	Temp. = 328.15 K				Temp. = 333.15 K			
10	17.82	65.64	282.1	14.72	20.51	60.59	276.1	14.44
20	16.48	63.13	284.4	14.85	19.07	54.54	265.9	13.92
30	15.43	60.55	280.6	14.64	17.77	48.13	256.7	13.41
40	12.44	57.86	273.5	14.31	18.72	41.66	277.4	14.51
50	11.86	55.10	274.1	14.32	16.99	35.34	273.3	14.28
60	11.76	51.52	276.4	14.43	14.87	29.73	265.4	13.89
70	8.61	47.79	297.5	15.55	12.55	24.87	259.2	13.49
	Temp. = 333.15 K							
10	27.64	63.98	277.6	14.53				
20	26.88	61.56	280.0	14.64				
30	24.21	58.97	276.0	14.45				
40	21.55	56.24	268.8	14.07				
50	19.94	53.36	268.8	14.09				
60	19.02	50.17	272.1	14.22				
70	14.67	46.33	292.0	15.32				

crease in the degree of solvent structuredness. This structure-making effect becomes saturated sooner with the larger alcohol molecules. It is then opposed by further addition of alcohol, so that the structure-making passes through a maximum. The gradual increase of ΔG^\ddagger with the mole fraction of both solvent mixtures gives a good indication of the pronounced solvation of the reactants in presence of organic solvent. Furthermore, the non-linear variation of ΔS^\ddagger is a criterion of specific solvation¹¹ and shows that the concept of random distribution of two components is not valid in the absence of strong hydrogen-bonding between water and the alcohol molecule. Moreover, the highly negative ΔS^\ddagger values support the formation of the intermediate complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{3+}$ which bears higher charge than the original complex, indicating a dissociative mechanism. The isokinetic plot ($\Delta H^\ddagger - \Delta S^\ddagger$) was found to be linear with an isokinetic temperature (β) of 312 and 340 K for n-propanol-water and glycerol-water

mixtures respectively. The values of β for both the solvent-water mixtures are fairly close to the experimental temperatures (318, 323 K) confirming the existence of the compensation effect where the solute-solvent interactions play an important role.

The variation of $\log k$ with $\log [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ is linear at constant temperature for different solvent compositions and the average value of the slopes obtained is found to be in the range 0.2–0.4 (less than unity) indicating that the internal structure of the media studied suffered serious changes on addition of the organic solvent component. The same behaviour was observed by Tomila *et al.*¹² indicating that hydrogen bond between organic solvent molecule and water is stronger than that between two water molecules. Thus hydrogen bonding between neighbouring water molecules will be replaced gradually by hydrogen bonding with solvent molecules and the tetrahedral structure of water is then largely broken.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS* OF ACTIVATED COMPLEX FOR THE AQUATION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

n-Propanol :

Wt%	X_2		E_c	308.15 K	318.15 K	323.15 K	333.15 K
10	0.032	ΔG^\ddagger	91.975	104.117	104.554	104.836	105.319
		ΔH^\ddagger		89.414	89.331	89.289	89.206
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		47.740	47.870	48.130	48.390
20	0.070	ΔG^\ddagger	88.591	103.975	104.559	104.851	105.439
		ΔH^\ddagger		86.030	85.947	85.905	85.822
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		58.260	58.530	58.660	58.910
30	0.114	ΔG^\ddagger	85.515	104.085	104.772	105.117	105.808
		ΔH^\ddagger		82.954	82.871	82.829	82.746
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		68.610	68.870	69.000	69.260
40	0.167	ΔG^\ddagger	92.417	104.356	104.828	105.064	105.541
		ΔH^\ddagger		89.856	89.773	89.731	89.648
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		47.080	47.340	47.470	47.730
50	0.231	ΔG^\ddagger	91.051	104.592	105.116	105.379	105.907
		ΔH^\ddagger		88.490	88.407	88.365	88.282
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		52.280	52.540	52.680	52.930
60	0.310	ΔG^\ddagger	88.410	104.626	105.238	105.544	106.159
		ΔH^\ddagger		85.849	85.766	85.724	85.641
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		60.970	61.230	61.360	61.610
70	0.412	ΔG^\ddagger	86.022	105.002	105.703	106.053	106.758
		ΔH^\ddagger		83.461	83.378	83.336	83.253
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		69.940	70.200	70.330	70.590

Glycerol :

Wt%	X_2		E_c	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	328.15 K	333.15 K
10	0.021	ΔG^\ddagger	92.575	103.20	103.63	104.07	104.29	104.51
		ΔH^\ddagger		90.06	89.97	89.89	89.85	89.81
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		43.37	43.64	43.90	44.03	44.16
20	0.047	ΔG^\ddagger	93.340	103.41	103.82	104.24	104.45	104.66
		ΔH^\ddagger		90.82	90.74	90.65	90.61	90.57
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		41.54	41.81	42.07	42.20	42.32
30	0.077	ΔG^\ddagger	92.080	103.51	103.97	104.44	104.67	104.90
		ΔH^\ddagger		89.56	89.48	89.39	89.35	89.31
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		46.04	46.31	46.57	46.70	46.82
40	0.115	ΔG^\ddagger	89.753	103.69	104.23	104.78	105.06	105.33
		ΔH^\ddagger		87.23	87.15	87.07	87.03	86.98
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		54.31	54.58	54.84	54.96	55.09
50	0.164	ΔG^\ddagger	89.929	103.93	104.47	105.02	105.30	105.57
		ΔH^\ddagger		87.41	87.33	87.24	87.20	87.16
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		54.51	54.78	55.04	55.17	55.30
60	0.227	ΔG^\ddagger	90.706	104.08	104.61	105.14	105.40	105.67
		ΔH^\ddagger		88.19	88.10	88.02	87.98	87.94
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		52.47	52.73	53.00	53.12	53.25
70	0.313	ΔG^\ddagger	97.606	105.27	105.61	105.95	106.12	106.29
		ΔH^\ddagger		95.09	95.00	94.92	94.88	94.84
		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$		33.62	33.89	34.15	34.28	34.40

* ΔG^\ddagger , E_c in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS in $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$.

El-Semongy and Amira¹³ proposed a general equation of the variation of specific rate constant (k) with the dielectric constant (D),

$$\log A/k = \frac{Eb}{2.303 R \log c/D}$$

where $\log c = \log a + 293.15b$; A is the frequency factor and a , b are Akerlof's empirical constants¹⁴. The plot of $\log A/k$ vs $Eb/\log(c/D)$ gives a straight line for each sol-

vent-water mixtures. This line passes through the origin with a slope equal to 0.0522 and 0.0525 for n-propanol-water, glycerol-water mixtures, being very close to the theoretical value (0.0522). This provides further applicability of the above equation.

Recently a new general equation¹⁵ has been suggested for the variation of rate constant (k) with the total number of moles ($n_1 + n_2$), where n_1 is the number of moles of H_2O

Fig. 1. Variation of ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger , and ΔS^\ddagger with mole fraction (X_2).

and n_2 the number of moles of organic solvent for any reaction. The correlation takes the mathematical form,

$$\ln k = \ln K_B T/h - \Delta\mu^\ddagger (n_1 + n_2)/RT$$

In this expression, plot of $\ln k$ vs $(n_1 + n_2)$ gives a straight line with a slope equal to $-\Delta\mu^\ddagger/RT$. The estimated values of the change in the chemical potential ($\Delta\mu^\ddagger$) at 333 K are found to be -304 and -207 J mol $^{-1}$ K in glycerol-water and n-propanol-water mixtures respectively.

In conclusion, a dissociative mechanism for the aqua-

tion of bromopentamminecobalt(III) ion in these solvent systems can be suggested based on the large ΔS^\ddagger values. This mechanism was proposed earlier¹⁶.

Experimental

The complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$ was prepared by the reported procedures¹⁷ and then converted to perchlorate salt from acidified solution of concentrated LiClO_4 by cooling in ice. The product was washed until free from acid using alcohol and ether and dried over silica gel. The kinetic measurement was followed by potentiometric titration of the released ion with a standard AgNO_3 solution¹⁸. A AgBr -coated wire dipped in a bromide solution of unknown concentration was connected to a quinhydrone half-cell by means of an agar- KNO_3 salt-bridge. The end-point of each titration was detected at zero potential of the cell with the aid of a long scale spot galvanometer. This method of analysis was selected due to its high reproducibility and its good agreement with the rate constant values obtained by a spectrophotometric method¹⁹ under similar conditions.

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